

Abstract

The urinary bladder urothelial are highly specialized epithelia that protect the underlying tissues from mechanical stress and seal them from the overlying fluid space. To better understand the maintaining permeability induced electrical potential roles played by urothelial in the bladder, we established a protocol of gravitation stress in toad urothelial, observed the transmembrane potential difference variation.

Method: The toad urothelial were mounted in a using chamber which the chamber was separated to two solution spaces, and stable with 0.9% saline solution. The electrodes were settled on the surface of each side of the preparation, serosal side definite as cathode. The using chamber was settled in the centrifugal rotor and under 300 rpm rotation to obtain a vertically +4G gravitation on serosal chamber 5min.

Result: a transient transmembrane potential difference increasing was observed after adding CaCl_2 (3% solution) in serosal chamber. The amplitude increasing phase included a rapid and a slowly ascending phase. In gravitation stressed urothelial preparation, CaCl_2 induced transient phase was significantly increased, furthermore the secondary slowly ascending phase was much more amplified on its amplitude axis and significantly prolonged on the time scale than that evoked in control preparations. The evoked total amplitude increasing were 10 times higher than that in control.

Conclusion: The urinary bladder epithelial layer has a structure which regulates ion permeability as a barrier. The tight junction plays an important role as the intercellular coupling in the apical side of the epithelial cell. On the other hand, it is known that the ion channel exists on the epithelial cell membrane and regulates the physiological process. The gravitation stress weakened the tight junction. The transmembrane potential difference was enhanced both on its amplitude and prolonged time. The gravitation stress induced hyperpolarization that evoked by CaCl_2 is one kind of Cl^- transfer from serosal chamber in which high Ca^{2+} in the urothelial basal membrane activated the calcium-activated chloride channels. This outwardly rectifying chloride channel induced hyperpolarization can be blocked by *Nppb*.

Key word Gravitation stress; Urothelial; Hyperpolarization

59 **Introduction**

60 The urothelial lines the inner surface of the urinary bladder, where it forms a tight
61 barrier that allows for retention of urine, while preventing the unregulated movement
62 of ions, solutes, and toxic metabolites across the epithelial barrier. The urothelial
63 permeability barrier is made up of three components: apical membrane, tight junctions,
64 and the trafficking mechanism that inserts and removes apical membrane in response
65 to filling and emptying of the bladder. The apical membrane contains specialized lipid
66 molecules and uroplakin proteins that appear to function in concert to reduce
67 permeability of the apical membrane to small molecules such as water, ammonia,
68 protons, and urea ^[1]. The tight junctions sharply restrict the movement of ions, such as
69 Na⁺, K⁺, and Cl⁻ ^[2]. The permeability barrier must be maintained even as the organ
70 undergoes cyclical changes in pressure as it fills and empties. Beyond furthering the
71 understanding of pressure induced barrier function, new analysis of the urothelial is
72 providing some updated information about the plaques (detergent-insoluble
73 membrane/protein domains) are formed at the apical plasma membrane of the surface
74 umbrella cells ^[3]. The mechanical stimuli such as pressure alter urothelial exocytic
75 and endocytic traffic ^[4]. The urothelial barrier to ion, solute, and toxin flux must also
76 adapt to large variations in pressure as the bladder fills. Defects in plaque assembly
77 increase membrane permeability and may lead to diseases such as vesicoureteral
78 reflux ^[5, 6]. Therefore, urothelial studies provided the clues of its sense to mechanical
79 stimuli such as pressure, and transduce changes in these stimuli into cellular events
80 such as membrane traffic. The studies indicated that increased pressure stimulates
81 exocytosis and endocytosis in umbrella cells and modulated by purinergic signaling
82 cascades, Ca²⁺, and cAMP ^[7]. Nothing is known about regulation of pressure induced
83 cross barrier electrical potential differences, however this is important for
84 understanding its physiological excitation. Future analysis of this pathway may lead to
85 a better understanding of mechanical stress-independent pathways of internalization.
86 In an Ussing chamber model, it is possible to analyse the urothelial layer potential
87 difference *in vitro*. Some reports suggested that protamine irrigating increased the

88 barrier permeability to urea, a 3.5% urea movement across the membrane, appeared
89 that the impairing of urothelial surface may increasing barrier in modulating both
90 charged and uncharged small molecule movement ^[8]. In human being, the urothelial
91 barrier deficits, suburothelial inflammation and sensory proteins expressed in the
92 bladder mucosa usually combined with detrusor underactivity. The expression of zona
93 occuldens-1, E-cadherin, tryptase and apoptosis levels in the suburothelium,
94 β 3-adrenoceptor, M2 and M3 muscarinic receptors, P2X3 receptor, and inducible and
95 endothelial nitric oxide synthase were involed. The lower E-cadherin expression,
96 lower expression of M2 and M3 muscarinic receptors, was detected in these patients
97 ^[9]. Urothelial dysfunction altered sensory protein expressions, prominent the impaired
98 urothelial signaling and sensory transduction pathways ^[10]. With the availability of
99 Ussing chamber model, we can explore the reason of ionic permeability that regulate
100 the transmembrane potential difference. Some studies demonstrate that using chamber
101 method is help to understand the urothelial undergoes characteristic function and
102 structural response to injury, provide an approach to defining how this process is
103 regulated. The understanding of this mechanism is able to acquire how the urothelial
104 repairs itself may lead to important insights into the care of the human being with
105 cystitis and may also shed light on the mechanisms by which bladder cancer develops
106 ^[11]. The environmental differences between the apical and basal surfaces of the
107 urothelial, such as osmotic pressure and hydrostatic pressure influence the tight
108 junction related barrier action. Especially, the complex fiber protein network is
109 constructed in the epithelial cell junction maintained the low permeability. It was
110 clarified that the mechanical stretch reduced 10 times of the resistance of the
111 transcranial electrical resistance (TER) and the umbrella cell junction resistance ^[12].
112 The membrane permeability and the membrane bound were changed by ion
113 permeabilization. In this study, we investigated the effect of gravity acceleration on
114 the ion permeability and excitability of the bladder epithelium.

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116 **Methods**

117 The toad (4 weeks, n = 10) was purchased from the experimental animal center of
118 Hainan medical college. The study protocol was approved by the ethics committee of
119 Hainan medical college. All animal experiments were performed in accordance with
120 the guidelines of the animal care and use committee of Hainan medical university.
121 The toads sacrificed by foramen magnum pithing. After midline incision from the
122 sciatic to the hypodermic center, the bladder body was separated by a glass probe. The
123 gap with the total urinary bladder body was removed, then stable in Ringer's solution
124 for 10 min, room temperature. The urinary bladder urothelial wall was separated to
125 two parts by ophthalmic scissors. One part was for control, while another part was for
126 gravitation stress test. The urothelial layer was mounted on the Ussing chamber,
127 therefore the Ussing chamber was consist of two chambers, apical membrane chamber
128 (apical chamber) and basement membrane chamber (serosal chamber). The chambers
129 were fulfilled with 0.9% sodium chloride solution and stabilized for 5 min, room
130 temperature (**Figure 1**). The Ussing chamber was vertically centrifuged at 300 rpm
131 5min to obtain a 4G acceleration on its basement membrane. This is the gravitation
132 stress induced mechanical shed urothelial preparation. After that the apical membrane
133 and basement membrane was settled with electrode, the serosal side definite as
134 cathode. The electrodes were connected to the polygraph device for recording the
135 transmembrane potential difference (TPD). The urothelial membrane was activated by
136 3% CaCl₂ solution on its serosal side. The enhanced potential amplitude and prolong
137 time were analyzed. In a compared study the mechanical shed urothelial layer, the
138 chemical shed with glycerin was prepared. For investigating the Ca²⁺ induced Cl⁻
139 movement crossing the urothelial layer, the chloride channel blocker *Nppb* was used
140 for observing calcium-sensitive chloride currents.

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154 **Figure 1. Ussing chamber for toad urothelial layer for transmembrane potential**
155 **difference testing**

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157 **Results**

158 In control intact urothelial layer, CaCl₂ activation induced an increasing amplitude of
159 transient transmembrane potential difference (TPD). The amplitude increased rising
160 phase included a rapid and a slowly ascending phase (**Figure 2a**, *). After the
161 transient increasing phase, the amplitude maintained for a long period (arrow mark).

162 In gravitation stress induced mechanical shed urothelial preparation, CaCl₂ induced
163 transient rising phase was significantly enhanced, furthermore the secondary slowly
164 ascending phase was much more amplified on its amplitude axis, and the duration was
165 significantly prolonged on the time scale than the control intact urothelial preparation.

166 The CaCl₂ evoked transient rising phase was 10 times enhanced than that in control
167 preparation (**Figure 2b**, **). The arrow mark indicated a typical secondary increasing
168 after the transient rising phase. This secondary increasing continuously 6 times
169 prolonged than the initial amplitude increasing (red arrow period). The urothelial

170 layer was largely hyperpolarized. **Figure 2c** shown the CaCl₂ activated TPD in
171 glycerin shed urothelial preparation. The chemical shed did not obtain the significant
172 increasing of CaCl₂ activated TPD. **Figure 2d** was the *Nppb* intervened TPD in
173 mechanical shed urothelial preparation. The TPD were significantly reduced because

174 of blocking the chloride channel which indicated that the main compound of the

175 CaCl₂ activated amplitude increasing was Cl⁻. This further revealed that the Cl⁻ current
176 induced the hyperpolarization in mechanical shed urothelial preparation.

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186 a. Control intact preparation; b. Gravitation stress shed preparation; c. Glycerin
187 skinned preparation; d. *Nppb* treated mechanical shed preparation

188 **Figure 2. Transmembrane potential differences in prepared urothelial layer**

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190 Conclusion

191 The bladder epithelial layer has a structure which regulates ion permeability as a
192 barrier, and tight binding plays an important role as the intercellular coupling in the
193 apical side of the epithelial cell. On the other hand, it is known that the ion channel
194 exists on the epithelial cell membrane and regulates the physiological process. It was
195 reported that the transurothelial electrical resistance decreased with the urinary tract
196 injury using protamine sulfate [13]. The mechanical stretch method is noticed as a
197 method to weaken the tight coupling structure by minimizing the cell membrane
198 damage unlike the chemical damage. Using this method, the gravitational stress (4G)
199 was added to the basal membrane. The apical membrane and basal membrane
200 permeability was deeply influence.

201 In control intact urothelial preparation, CaCl₂ activated the Ca²⁺-activated chloride
202 channels (CaCCs), induced a amplitude increasing of the TPD. This increasing make
203 the urothelial to be in a slightly hyperpolarization on its apical membrane, therefore

204 protect the apical membrane from the over excitation. The experiment results
205 indicated that in the mechanical shed urothelial preparation, this hyperpolarization
206 was drastic enhanced. The membrane excitation was inhibited by the significant Cl⁻
207 movement from the basal membrane toward to the apical membrane. In contrast, there
208 was no significant increasing of such inhibition in chemical shed urothelial
209 preparation.

210 The Using chamber using for investigating the mechanical shed urothelial
211 permeability is a new challenged laboratory protocol for study the urothelial
212 physiological excitation during chemical compound intervened. This will help to
213 develop the new drug absorption system to improve the urinary bladder osmotic
214 therapy.

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216 **Conflict of interest**

217 There is no conflict of interest to be disclosed with respect to the conflict of interest.

218

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